

Statement of participation

Srignana Lokesh Ezhil

has completed the free course including any mandatory tests for:

Introducing healthcare improvement

This 3-hour course explored quality improvement in healthcare settings.

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www.open.edu/openlearn

This statement does not imply the award of credit points nor the conferment of a University Qualification.
This statement confirms that this free course and all mandatory tests were passed by the learner.

Please go to the course on OpenLearn for full details:

<https://www.open.edu/openlearn/health-sports-psychology/health/introducing-healthcare-improvement/content-section-0>

COURSE CODE: **K827_1**

Introducing healthcare improvement

<https://www.open.edu/openlearn/health-sports-psychology/health/introducing-healthcare-improvement/content-section-0>

Course summary

This free course, Introducing healthcare improvement, explores quality improvement in healthcare settings. It begins by defining healthcare quality and describing the meaning of quality improvement in healthcare. You will also learn about the different dimensions of quality and the broad aims of healthcare improvement. The course will help you better understand how and why we seek to improve healthcare quality.

Learning outcomes

By completing this course, the learner should be able to:

- define what is meant by quality improvement in healthcare
- describe the different dimensions of quality improvement in healthcare.

Completed study

The learner has completed the following:

Section 1

Defining and evaluating quality improvement in healthcare

Section 2

Six aims of quality in healthcare